

Supplementary Materials for:
A Hierarchical Bayesian Decision Tool for Empirical Antibiotic
Selection in Rural Australian Hospitals Using Regional
Susceptibility Priors

Hayden Farquhar MBBS MPHTM
Independent Researcher, Finley, New South Wales, Australia

Supplementary Methods

S1. Complete Model Specification

S1.1 Prior Construction

For each pathogen p and antibiotic d , the regional prior $\text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)$ was constructed as follows:

1. **ATLAS mean susceptibility** (μ_{ATLAS}): proportion susceptible from ATLAS Oceania 2018–2024 aggregate data.
2. **Community-onset correction**: μ_{ATLAS} was adjusted upward by $\Delta_{\text{community}}$ pp to estimate community-acquired susceptibility from the mixed-onset surveillance aggregate. Correction magnitudes (Supplementary Table S2) were derived from published comparisons of community versus hospital-onset susceptibility.
3. **Australian upweighting**: where AGAR data provided an Australian-specific estimate (μ_{AGAR}), the combined estimate was $\mu = 0.6 \times \mu_{\text{AGAR}} + 0.4 \times \mu_{\text{ATLAS_corrected}}$. AGAR estimates were first adjusted for CLSI/EUCAST breakpoint differences (Supplementary Table S3).
4. **Drug-specific sigma**: $\sigma = \sigma_{\text{base}} \times \sqrt{\mu(1-\mu)}/0.5$, where $\sigma_{\text{base}} = 0.05$. This scales the assumed between-hospital standard deviation proportionally to the natural binomial standard deviation, ensuring near-certain drugs receive appropriately narrow priors.
5. **Beta parameterisation**: $\alpha = \mu \times (\mu(1-\mu)/\sigma^2 - 1)$; $\beta = (1-\mu) \times (\mu(1-\mu)/\sigma^2 - 1)$.
6. **Convenience-sample downweighting**: $\alpha_{\text{eff}} = \alpha \times d$; $\beta_{\text{eff}} = \beta \times d$, where $d = 0.5$ (primary analysis), $d \in \{0.25, 0.5, 1.0\}$ (sensitivity).

S1.2 Conjugate Posterior Update

Given local antibiogram data (n_{local} isolates tested, k_{local} susceptible):

$$\theta \mid \text{data} \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_{\text{eff}} + k_{\text{local}}, \beta_{\text{eff}} + n_{\text{local}} - k_{\text{local}})$$

The prior weight (proportion of posterior information from the prior) is:

$$w_{\text{prior}} = \frac{\alpha_{\text{eff}} + \beta_{\text{eff}}}{\alpha_{\text{eff}} + \beta_{\text{eff}} + n_{\text{local}}}$$

S1.3 Antibiogram Age Decay

For antibiogram data of age a months:

$$\begin{aligned} n_{\text{effective}} &= n_{\text{local}} \times 0.5^{a/12} \\ k_{\text{effective}} &= k_{\text{local}} \times 0.5^{a/12} \end{aligned}$$

Both rounded to integers. A 12-month-old antibiogram contributes 50% of its original weight.

S1.4 Correlated Drug Updates

When local data for drug A shows a deviation $\delta_A = (k_A/n_A) - \mu_A$ from the prior mean, correlated drug B (with co-resistance coefficient ρ_{AB}) receives an adjustment:

$$\mu_{B_adjusted} = \mu_{B_posterior} + \rho_{AB} \times \delta_A$$

This propagation only applies to drugs without their own local data and only when $|\delta_A| > 0.02$.

S1.5 Sigmoid Susceptibility Utility

$$f(p) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\kappa \times (p - t))}$$

where $\kappa = 20$ (steepness) and t is the severity-dependent threshold:

Severity	Threshold
Stable	0.75
Moderate	0.80
Severe	0.85
Critical	0.90

S1.6 OR-Based Combination Coverage

For a combination of drugs $\{d_1, d_2\}$ against pathogen p :

$$P(\text{at least one effective}) = 1 - P(\text{both resistant})$$

$$P(\text{both R}) = P(R_{d_1}) \times P(R_{d_2}) + \rho \times \sigma_{R_1} \times \sigma_{R_2}$$

where ρ is the co-resistance correlation and $\sigma_{R_i} = \sqrt{P(R_{d_i})(1 - P(R_{d_i}))}$.

S1.7 Gram Stain Conditional Update

Pathogen probabilities $P(p|\text{syndrome})$ were updated via Bayes' rule:

$$P(p|\text{Gram stain, syndrome}) \propto P(\text{Gram stain}|p) \times P(p|\text{syndrome})$$

Pre-specified likelihood ratios $P(\text{Gram stain}|\text{pathogen})$:

Gram stain result	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
GPC clusters	0.01	0.90	0.02	0.01	0.01
GPC chains/diplococci	0.01	0.05	0.90	0.01	0.01
GNR	0.40	0.01	0.01	0.25	0.20

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1. Complete Regional Prior Parameters (30 combinations)

Pathogen	Antibiotic	μ_{ATLAS}	$\Delta_{\text{comm.}}$	μ_{AGAR}	μ_{combined}	$\alpha_{\text{eff}}/\beta_{\text{eff}}$	Source
<i>E. coli</i>	Amox-clav	0.867	+0.030	0.906	0.902	44.7/4.9	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>E. coli</i>	Ceftazidime	0.878	+0.040	—	0.918	45.4/4.1	ATLAS
<i>E. coli</i>	Ceftriaxone	—	—	0.871	0.871	43.1/6.4	AGAR
<i>E. coli</i>	Ciprofloxacin	0.797	+0.050	0.865	0.852	42.2/7.3	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>E. coli</i>	Gentamicin	0.901	+0.030	0.919	0.924	45.7/3.8	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>E. coli</i>	Levofloxacin	0.818	—	—	0.818	40.5/9.0	ATLAS
<i>E. coli</i>	Meropenem	0.998	+0.001	0.998	0.998	49.4/0.1	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>E. coli</i>	Pip-tazo	0.944	+0.020	0.980*	0.950	47.0/2.5	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Amox-clav	0.932	+0.020	0.912	0.928	45.9/3.6	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Ceftazidime	0.913	+0.030	—	0.943	46.7/2.8	ATLAS
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Ceftriaxone	—	—	0.931	0.931	46.1/3.4	AGAR
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Ciprofloxacin	0.873	+0.030	0.932*	0.914	45.2/4.2	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Gentamicin	0.954	+0.020	0.955	0.963	47.6/1.8	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Levofloxacin	0.904	—	—	0.904	44.7/4.8	ATLAS
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Meropenem	0.993	+0.001	0.994	0.994	49.2/0.3	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Pip-tazo	0.925	+0.020	0.956*	0.922	45.6/3.9	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Ceftazidime	0.906	—	—	0.906	44.8/4.7	ATLAS
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Ciprofloxacin	0.895	+0.020	0.924	0.921	45.6/3.9	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Gentamicin	0.938	—	0.938	0.938	46.4/3.1	ATLAS
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Levofloxacin	0.834	—	—	0.834	41.3/8.2	ATLAS
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Meropenem	0.926	+0.010	0.921	0.927	45.9/3.6	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Pip-tazo	0.893	+0.020	0.863	0.883	43.7/5.8	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>S. aureus</i>	Ciprofloxacin	0.947	—	—	0.947	46.9/2.6	ATLAS
<i>S. aureus</i>	Gentamicin	0.963	—	0.978	0.972	48.1/1.4	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>S. aureus</i>	Levofloxacin	0.931	—	—	0.931	46.1/3.4	ATLAS
<i>S. aureus</i>	Vancomycin	1.000	—	1.000	1.000	49.5/0.0	ATLAS+AGAR
<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	Ceftriaxone	0.955	—	—	0.955	47.3/2.2	ATLAS
<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	Levofloxacin	0.996	—	—	0.996	49.3/0.2	ATLAS
<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	Meropenem	0.878	—	—	0.878	43.5/6.0	ATLAS
<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	Vancomycin	1.000	—	—	0.999	49.5/0.0	ATLAS

*Adjusted for CLSI/EUCAST breakpoint difference. — indicates data not available from that source.

Supplementary Table S2. Community-Onset Susceptibility Corrections

Pathogen	Antibiotic	Correction (pp)	Basis
<i>E. coli</i>	Ceftriaxone/ceftazidime	+4	ESBL prevalence lower in community
<i>E. coli</i>	Ciprofloxacin	+5	Prior FQ exposure more common in hospital
<i>E. coli</i>	Amox-clav	+3	Moderate hospital-community difference
<i>E. coli</i>	Pip-tazo	+2	Smaller difference for broad-spectrum
<i>E. coli</i>	Gentamicin	+3	Moderate difference
<i>E. coli</i>	Meropenem	+0.1	Negligible — near-universal susceptibility
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	All drugs	+2–3	Similar pattern, smaller magnitude
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Cipro/pip-tazo/meropenem	+1–2	Less clear community/hospital distinction
<i>S. aureus</i>	Ciprofloxacin	+2	Community MRSA rate lower

Supplementary Table S3. CLSI/EUCAST Breakpoint Corrections

Pathogen	Antibiotic	EUCAST BP	CLSI BP	Correction
Enterobacterales	Pip-tazo	S \leq 8 mg/L	S \leq 16/4 mg/L	+4–5pp to AGAR
Enterobacterales	Ciprofloxacin	S \leq 0.25 mg/L	S \leq 0.25 mg/L	+1pp (minor)

Supplementary Table S4. Co-Resistance Correlation Coefficients

Pathogen	Drug A	Drug B	ρ	Basis
<i>E. coli</i>	Ceftriaxone	Ciprofloxacin	0.35	ESBL + FQ co-resistance (AGAR)
<i>E. coli</i>	Ceftriaxone	Gentamicin	0.20	ESBL + aminoglycoside
<i>E. coli</i>	Ceftriaxone	Pip-tazo	0.30	Shared beta-lactam resistance
<i>E. coli</i>	Ciprofloxacin	Gentamicin	0.15	Weak co-resistance
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Ceftriaxone	Ciprofloxacin	0.30	Similar to <i>E. coli</i>
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Ceftriaxone	Gentamicin	0.20	Similar to <i>E. coli</i>
Cross-class	Beta-lactam	Vancomycin	0.00	Independent mechanisms

Supplementary Table S5. Utility Weight Sets

Weight	Primary	A (suscept.)	B (cost)	C (collateral)	D (equal)
$w_{\text{susceptibility}}$	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
w_{cost}	0.05	0.0	0.20	0.05	0.10
w_{cdiff}	0.15	0.0	0.15	0.30	0.10
w_{spectrum}	0.10	0.0	0.10	0.20	0.10
w_{allergy}	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50

Supplementary Table S6. Sensitivity to Local Sample Size

n_{local}	MAE (Bayesian)	MAE (Local)	Brier skill	Prior weight	Bayesian > local
10	0.031	0.081	87.5%	0.453	98.8%
30	0.023	0.039	67.0%	0.252	95.0%
100	0.015	0.018	35.9%	0.100	87.4%
300	0.009	0.010	8.3%	0.037	76.6%

Supplementary Table S7. Weight Set Concordance Matrix

Percentage of scenarios where two weight sets produce the same #1 recommendation (2,000 scenarios).

	Primary	A	B	C	D
Primary	100.0	62.5	80.3	77.2	93.9
A (suscept.)	62.5	100.0	51.8	48.4	62.5
B (cost)	80.3	51.8	100.0	96.2	86.5
C (collateral)	77.2	48.4	96.2	100.0	83.3
D (equal)	93.9	62.5	86.5	83.3	100.0

Supplementary Table S8. Brier Score Decomposition

n_{local}	Brier (Bay)	Brier (Loc)	Reliab. (Bay)	Reliab. (Loc)	Sharp. (Bay)	Sharp. (Loc)
10	0.00124	0.00991	0.00000	0.00742	0.00266	0.00754
30	0.00093	0.00282	0.00000	0.00136	0.00296	0.00548
100	0.00049	0.00077	0.00000	0.00016	0.00340	0.00442

Reliability = calibration error (lower is better). Sharpness = variance of predictions (higher indicates more discriminating predictions). Bayesian reliability is zero by conjugate construction.

Supplementary Table S9. Expected Value of Perfect Information by Syndrome

Syndrome	$E[U]$ posterior	$E[U]$ perfect	EVPI	EVPI %
CAP severe	0.520	0.520	<0.001	<0.1%
CAP moderate	0.337	0.337	<0.001	<0.1%
UTI/pyelonephritis	0.694	0.694	0.001	0.1%
Intra-abdominal	0.439	0.443	0.004	0.9%
SSTI severe	0.519	0.519	<0.001	<0.1%
Bacteraemia unknown	0.594	0.594	<0.001	0.1%
Meningitis	0.518	0.517	<0.001	<0.1%

Supplementary Table S10. Effective Prior Sample Size

All priors have effective sample size ($\alpha_{\text{eff}} + \beta_{\text{eff}}$) \approx 49.5 isolates. Local data dominates the posterior (prior weight \leq 50%) when $n_{\text{local}} > 50$ isolates. This uniformity is a consequence of the drug-specific sigma scaling, which produces similar effective concentrations across all drugs regardless of susceptibility level.

Supplementary Table S11. Face-Validity Clinical Scenarios (Summary)

Twenty curated clinical scenarios were generated spanning all seven syndromes. For each scenario, the tool's recommendation, expected utility, and concordance with eTG first-line are reported. The full scenario vignettes with detailed tool output are available in the code repository.

#	Syndrome	Local data	Allergies	Tool recommendation	eTG
1	CAP severe	14 <i>E. coli</i>	None	Ceftriaxone + gentamicin	Yes
2	CAP moderate	None	Beta-lactam	Ceftriaxone	No
3	CAP severe	8 <i>S. pneum.</i>	None	Ceftriaxone + gentamicin	Yes
4	UTI	45 <i>E. coli</i> (4 drugs)	None	Gentamicin	No
5	UTI	6 <i>E. coli</i>	Fluoroquinolone	Gentamicin	No
6	UTI	30 <i>E. coli</i> (low cipro)	Aminoglycoside	Pip-tazo	No
7	Intra-abdom.	25 <i>E. coli</i>	None	Pip-tazo	No
8	Intra-abdom.	None	Beta-lactam (anaph.)	Pip-tazo	No
9	Intra-abdom.	120 <i>E. coli</i> + 40 <i>K. pn.</i>	None	Pip-tazo	No
10	SSTI severe	50 <i>S. aureus</i>	None	Pip-tazo + vancomycin	Yes
11	SSTI severe	10 <i>S. aureus</i>	Glycopeptide	Pip-tazo + vancomycin	Yes
12	Bacteraemia	30 <i>E. coli</i> + 20 <i>S. aureus</i>	None	Pip-tazo + vancomycin	Yes
13	Bacteraemia	None (new hospital)	None	Pip-tazo + vancomycin	Yes
14	Bacteraemia	20 <i>E. coli</i> + 15 <i>S. aureus</i>	High CDI risk	Pip-tazo + vancomycin	Yes
15	Meningitis	5 <i>S. pneum.</i>	None	Ceftriaxone + vancomycin	Yes
16	Meningitis	3 <i>S. pneum.</i>	Cephalosporin	Meropenem	No
17	UTI (edge)	30 <i>E. coli</i> (50% ceftriaxone S)	None	Gentamicin	No
18	CAP severe	100 <i>E. coli</i> + 30 <i>S. pneum.</i>	None	Ceftriaxone + gentamicin	Yes
19	SSTI severe	20 <i>S. aureus</i>	BL + aminoglyc.	Pip-tazo + vancomycin	Yes
20	Intra-abdom.	40 <i>E. coli</i> (12-mo old)	None	Pip-tazo	No

These scenarios are awaiting review by 3–5 rural Australian ED/GP/ID physicians.

Supplementary Checklist S1. TRIPOD+AI Compliance

TRIPOD+AI Item	Status	Location
1. Title identifies prediction model study	Yes	Title
2. Structured abstract	Yes	Synopsis
3a. Background and objectives	Yes	Introduction
4a. Data sources and study setting	Yes	Methods: Data Sources
4b. Study dates	Yes	Methods (ATLAS 2018–2024; AGAR 2023)
5a. Participants/eligibility	Yes	Methods
6a. Outcome definition	Yes	Methods
7a. Predictor definition	Yes	Methods
8. Sample size	Yes	Methods (5,613 + 10,453)
10a. Statistical methods	Yes	Methods
10b. Model building	Yes	Methods
10d. Missing data handling	Yes	Methods
12. Model specification	Yes	Methods (equations)
13a. Participants flow	N/A	(simulation)
14a. Model performance	Yes	Results
15a. Interpretation	Yes	Discussion
16. Limitations	Yes	Discussion: Limitations
19. Supplementary information	Yes	This document
20. Code and data availability	Yes	Data Availability
AI-1. AI model description	Yes	Methods
AI-2. AI performance metrics	Yes	Results

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure S1. Bayesian shrinkage behaviour for *Escherichia coli* ciprofloxacin (local rate 70%, regional prior 85.2%).

Supplementary Figure S2. Decision curve analysis for *E. coli* ciprofloxacin at $n_{\text{local}} = 30$.

Supplementary Figure S3. Effective prior sample size by pathogen and antibiotic (horizontal bar chart).

Supplementary Figure S4. Expected value of perfect information (EVPI) by syndrome (horizontal bar chart).

Supplementary Figure S5. ATLAS Oceania susceptibility overview by pathogen and antibiotic, 2018–2024.

Supplementary Code and Data Availability

Two repositories are provided under MIT licence:

RUBIE decision tool (standalone interactive application):

- Web application: <https://rubie-tool.streamlit.app>
- Source code: <https://github.com/hayden-farquhar/rubie>
- Zenodo DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19657288>

Key tool files:

- `rubie/model.py` — conjugate Beta-Binomial model
- `rubie/utility.py` — decision-theoretic utility ranking
- `rubie/adjustments.py` — co-resistance, sigmoid, severity, and Gram stain adjustments
- `rubie/config/utility_config.yaml` — frozen drug-level parameters
- `rubie/config/syndrome_regimens.yaml` — syndrome-regimen mappings
- `rubie/config/regional_priors.yaml` — computed regional priors

Manuscript reproducibility code (analysis, simulation, figures):

- Source code: <https://github.com/hayden-farquhar/Rural-Antibiotic-Bayesian>
- Zenodo DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19650095>

Key analysis files:

- `src/validation/simulation_calibration.py` — Monte Carlo simulation (10,000 scenarios)
- `src/validation/statistical_validation.py` — decision curve, Brier, EVPI analyses
- `src/validation/sensitivity_analyses.py` — utility weight and downweighting sensitivity
- `src/validation/face_validity_scenarios.py` — 20 curated clinical scenarios

Pre-registration: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/GUCZN>